

TABLE I: Real-world Temporal Graph inputs and their key properties.

Datasets	$ V $	$ E $	$ E / V $
sx-Stackoverflow [1]	6024270	57724802	10
enron [2]	87273	594912	7
sx-mathoverflow [3]	88580	375972	4
fb-wall [4]	63891	366824	6

(i) 10% pre-initialization

(ii) 30% pre-initialization

(a) sx-stackoverflow

(i) 10% pre-initialization

(ii) 30% pre-initialization

(b) enron

(i) 10% pre-initialization

(ii) 30% pre-initialization

(c) sx-mathoverflow

(i) 10% pre-initialization

(ii) 30% pre-initialization

(d) fb-wall

Fig. 1: The relationship between vertex' base degree and their expected new edge insertions. x-axis is the degree in log-scale; y-axis is the expected insertions. This plot is an extension of Fig. 5 of our paper. Here we include results for four different real-world temporal graphs in 10% and 30% pre-initialization cases. sx-stackoverflow graph with 30% pre-initialization case was presented in the paper as Fig. 5(b).

Graphs	10% pre-initialization		30% pre-initialization	
	Count of new vertices inserted during the dynamic insertion	% of new vertices inserted during the dynamic insertion	Count of new vertices inserted during the dynamic insertion	% of new vertices inserted during the dynamic insertion
sx-stackoverflow	2379918	39.51%	1863049	30.93%
enron	75567	86.59%	59290	67.94%
sx-mathoverflow	22336	25.22%	18691	21.10%
fb-wall	37826	59.20%	30618	47.92%

TABLE II: Statistical results showing the newly arrived vertices during the dynamic insertion phase in real-world temporal graphs. Results include both the 10% and 30% pre-initialization cases.

Reference:

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 2. Bryan Klimt and Yiming Yang. The Enron corpus: A new dataset for email classification research. In Proc. Eur. Conf. on Mach. Learn., pages 217–226, 2004.
 3. Ashwin Paranjape, Austin R. Benson, and Jure Leskovec. "Motifs in Temporal Networks." In Proceedings of the Tenth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, 2017.
 4. tdGraphEmbed: Temporal Dynamic Graph-Level Embedding. Moran Beladev, Lior Rokach, Gilad Katz, Ido Guy, Kira Radinsky. CIKM'20 – October 2020, Galway, Ireland.